

THE ROLE AND FUNCTIONAL DYNAMICS OF WORD GROUPS IN INTERLINGUISTIC RELATIONS

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Abstract. *The development of language is inseparable from interlingual relations. It is an undeniable fact that interlingual relations play a significant and serious role in the development of language. In linguistic literature, interlingual relations are interpreted as changes that occur in one language under the influence of another during the contact of two languages. Although the history of studying interlingual relations and language development issues in linguistics covers a considerable period of time, it has not yet found its full scientific analysis. Therefore, it is one of the urgent problems that needs to be studied. The role of interlingual relations in the development of the mentioned languages is an issue that is absolutely worthy of comprehensive study. There is an urgent need to filter the research devoted to the indicated field, to generalize the ideas formed on the issue, to clarify the conditions and reasons for the emergence of relations between languages, to determine the linguistic and psychological reasons that arise in individual speeches during acquaintance with a foreign language.*

Two main factors have been identified in the development of languages. They are called intra-linguistic and extra-linguistic factors. Interlingual relations are an external factor of language development. The term interlingual relations itself reflects the mutual relations between languages of the same and different systems. When interconnection between languages continue for a long time, many of the cases of deviation from the language norm become the norm and can gain citizenship in the language.

Modern linguistics associates the changes occurring in the scientific language with a number of reasons, a set of reasons. However, there is no unified opinion among linguists on this position” [8, 451]. There is a lot of interest in the problem of language relations, which covers basically all areas of the language. “Scientists who study the problems of language development can be divided into several groups. The first group of scientists includes the romantics, to whom Schlegel and the Grimm brothers, as well as W. Humboldt, belonged. In their opinion, languages that have reached their highest level have lost their beautiful past in connection with the decline of the national spirit” [12, 466]. However, the fallacy of these ideas gives reason to disagree with them.

Key words: *language relations, linguistics, language development, bilingualism, multilingualism, borrowings and loan words.*

Introduction - Borrowed words are used in all languages of the world. Borrowed words are noticeable at all linguistic levels. That is, they differ according to their types. When we say borrowings, we should not only understand borrowed words. Therefore, there is a significant difference between borrowings and loanwords. When we say borrowings, a broad concept arises in the mind. Borrowings are not only in the lexical layer of the language and are not confined to the lexical layer. Research on

interlingual relations is based on the fact that the change and development of the language are its main feature. In modern linguistics, both interlingual relations and the development of languages are considered the most important, main issues. “The development of a language, which is a complex dynamic system, cannot occur under the influence of a single factor.

We cannot look at their limitation and narrow framing only in the lexicon. Because borrowings are more prominent in the lexicon [3,25]. The study of borrowings is of great importance for both the theory of language contacts and general linguistics. This is the reason why the study of the borrowing process in linguistics began in ancient times. “Philosophers of various nations understood this truth in ancient times. Ancient Indian and Greek scholars interested in linguistics touched on this issue 2000 years ago and more” [10, 25].

Bilingualism and multilingualism were widespread both in ancient times and in modern times. Some linguists say that bilingualism exists only between genetically different, that is, unrelated languages. Some linguists call bilingualism a speaker of any two languages, or even knowledge of two closely related languages. There are more supporters of the second idea.

It is impossible to associate the comprehensive study of interlingual relations in world linguistics with ancient times. True, 2000 years ago, ancient Indian and Greek scholars who were interested in linguistic issues expressed certain ideas about borrowings, which are the simplest but most widespread form of these relations. Starting with V. Humboldt, this issue was approached in linguistics in a more serious and scientific way. Interest in this area began from the time when scientific linguistics was formed. The works of V. Humboldt, the founder of modern general linguistics, touched on the problem of language relations, which are considered extralinguistic factors.

The scientific study of interlingual relations was first encountered in the works of the Austrian linguist H. Schuhardt. H. Schuhardt, who sharply criticized the ideas of young grammarians about the development of language, saw the laws of language development in the mixing of languages. In his article “On the Problem of Language Mixture”, the problem of language mixing is considered the most urgent among the areas of linguistics. He put forward the idea that the problem of language mixing is not physiological, but always social, and said that there is no language in the world that does not mix, does not reflect foreign elements. He stated that he did not recognize any restrictions on the possibility of language mixing. “Contacts between languages can lead to both maximal and minimal differences” [13, 179]. H. Schuhardt rightly linked the problem of language mixing with the problem of bilingualism. In his opinion, “the mixing of languages occurs as a result of the migration of peoples, but this process can occur only if they constantly live in the same territory.

Change and development are also considered as the main characteristics of language. The development of languages is one of the most important problems studied by modern linguistics. It is a fact that interlingual relations play a significant role in the development of language. Interlingual relations refer to changes that occur in one language under the influence of another during the contact of two languages.

Comparative study of languages with different systems allows for interesting and successful results. The factors influencing the great interest in the study of both

related and foreign languages by the comparative-contrastive method are: 1. Comparative study of languages enriches the science of linguistics with new valuable knowledge, information about its connection with thinking and cognition; 2. Studies of this content make it possible to clarify the laws that are common to all languages or language groups, but also specific to a language taken separately; 3. The study of languages by this method plays a decisive role in determining the similarities and differences between the facts of different languages; 4. The results obtained as a result of the study of word groups that differ in their scope of use in different languages provide a great help in translation work, the compilation of bilingual and multilingual dictionaries; 5. The study of languages with this method makes it possible to create textbooks and teaching aids for foreign languages.

The study of lexical units on the basis of various systematic language units is very important for bringing some clarity to the linguistic nature of existing lexical-semantic word groups. L.V. Shcherba wrote: “The vast majority of words cannot be equated with the concepts of any language, words, concepts of any other language, and cannot be compared, only terms are an exception” [11, 320].

The fact that linguistics is a science that has undergone a great development from the most ancient times to the present day makes it possible to call lexicology an ancient field of that science. Since the religious and philosophical collections known as the object of study of ancient Indian linguistics - the Vedas, whose date of creation is believed to be 1500 years before our era, are of particular interest, the literature on these inscriptions, that is, the literature in which they are explained, reflects the ideas and worldviews of Indian scholars related to linguistics, and a certain scientific attitude is expressed to the issues of lexicology and etymology [2, 8].

The fact that this interesting science, which provides the main communication and exchange of ideas between people, is more than 2500 years old, proves its antiquity. Therefore, there is great truth in the opinion of those who write that the science of linguistics reached a high level of development in the 19th century, and that it is impossible to compare any of the previous centuries with the successes of the indicated period [7, 25].

The schools of linguistics of the ancient period differed from each other in the level of research they conducted in various branches of linguistics. For example: The achievements and successes of ancient Indian linguistics in the field of lexicology are not so significant. The work done by Indian linguistics in the fields of lexicology and lexicography cannot be compared with the work done by Arab linguists [9, 18].

“When studying languages, first of all, their diversity amazes us - that diversity that is observed both in different countries and within the same country” [4, 338].

Analogously, we can say that certain linguistic similarities between languages with different systems also arouse admiration in a person. Change and development are considered the main feature of language. The issue of language development is one of the most important problems that modern linguistics deals with. The evolution and development of language are called very complex analyses. The specific features of its development confirm this once again. The development of society ensures the development of thinking, and the development of thinking ensures the development of language. The connection of language development with thinking arises from their internal unity and mutual relations.

The development of language generally refers to the regular change and enrichment of the components of the main means of communication - sounds, suffixes, words, word combinations, sentences, and grammatical categories. "There are two sides to the development of a language: the development of the language under the influence of the external environment and the internal development of the language. In the development of any language, these factors are closely related to each other. Therefore, this problem poses a very significant difficulty in the study of language changes [6, 198].

Since words in the modern Azerbaijani literary language differ from each other not only in terms of their origin, active and passive in speech, but also in terms of their scope of use, they are grouped under the names of common words, words used in a limited circle, and special words. Of these word groups, common words are called the basis of the vocabulary of the language, and it is shown that it is impossible to imagine the language without them. That is, the correct opinion was expressed about the position of common words in the vocabulary of the language [5, 73].

The study realizes the relevance of scientific and theoretical provisions confirmed by specific word facts within the separate layers-tiers of the languages being compared. Currently, great attention is paid to gaining great influence of the Azerbaijani language in the system of international relations as an official state language, We consider it appropriate to emphasize that the enrichment of the language and its recognition at the required level among the peoples of the world create a stimulus for its comparative study with foreign languages at all levels.

During the typological study of the lexical units of the language, by comparing the paradigmatic order of structural-semantic and communicative-stylistic variants, wide opportunities open up for identifying common as well as different aspects between languages of different systems.

As in the case of the comparative-historical method used in the study of related languages, the use of the comparative comparison method in the study of word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use in foreign languages also gives positive results. The study of that word group in unrelated languages is of great importance for typological linguistics.

Word groups and word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use express different concepts. Linguistics is a scientific study of language. It can be likened to a compass that guides the correct use of scientific language units. However, in some textbooks on linguistics, we see that the terms are not used precisely. For example, in one of the sources, the term lexicon of the Azerbaijani literary language is used instead of word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use [1, 127], [6, 198].

Correctly determining the places of semantic groups of lexical units that differ in terms of their scope of use in different systematic languages (Azerbaijani and English), explaining their national, as well as universal features, essences at the level of the requirements of modern general linguistics, analyzing the areas of use, usage features, and specific stylistic shades of meaning of these word groups is relevant both theoretically and practically.

Conclusion - We see a certain change in the lexical composition of the language in the example of word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use. This should be considered natural. These word groups reflect various entities and phenomena of

objective reality. Passing these word groups, which contain a certain part of the lexical-semantic system of the language, through an analytical filter based on the colorful materials that make up the system, is of particular importance with a number of specific aspects.

Comparative study of word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use in modern Azerbaijani and English languages is of particular importance. Thus, the study of lexical units that differ in terms of their scope of use in languages included in different systems illustrates the indicators of languages in that direction, and research in this direction allows us to obtain a clear idea of the lexical system of the Azerbaijani and English languages, their development.

The study of the functions, national and universal aspects of lexical units belonging to word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use in the Azerbaijani and English languages, and the analysis of their specific stylistic nuances are both theoretically and practically relevant.

In an era when the socio-economic, literary-cultural, etc. relations of Azerbaijan with world states are expanding, the necessity of studying English not only as any foreign language, but also as a language of politics, diplomacy, and business relations should be specially noted. That is why it is relevant to conduct a comparative linguistic analysis of word groups that differ in terms of their scope of use in languages of different systems (Azerbaijani and English).

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